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Research Article

Formulation Evaluation & Optimization Of Vildagliptin Sustained Release Tablet

Abhay Sawant*, S. D. Barhate, M. M. Bari, Yogesh Sonawane, Amol Chaudhari, Reema Jagnit

Department of Pharmaceutics, Shree Sureshdada Jain Institute of Pharmaceutical Education & Research
Jamner Dist Jalgaon 424206 Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the current study was to create vildagliptin tablets with sustained release. Due to its brief biological half-life (2–3 hours), this medication is thought to be appropriate for sustained release tablet formulation in order to extend its therapeutic effect. Vildagliptin is a novel dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor class of oral antihyperglycemic medication.

Materials and Method:

Wet granulation was used to prepare the SR tablets, with varying ratios of synthetic polymers. Granules were prepared, and their compressibility index, Hausner's ratio, bulk density, and tapped density were assessed. Utilized Statistical Analysis: The vildagliptin and various polymers' individual and combined Fourier-transform infrared spectra demonstrate the medication's compatibility with excipients.

Results:

It was discovered that the tablets' physicochemical characteristics were within tolerance. The weight variation, thickness, hardness, percentage friability, percentage drug content, and in vitro release of the prepared tablets were assessed. Using a USP dissolution rate test apparatus II (50 rpm, 37 °C ± 0.5 °C) as the dissolution medium, in vitro dissolution studies were conducted for two hours in 0.1 N HCl (1.2 pH) and then for 10 hours in 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Conclusion :

The maximum drug release of 91.03% was observed in 12 hours of dissolution for the optimized formulation F5. Formulation F5's release kinetic data revealed zero order (R² = 9902).

*Corresponding Author: Abhay Sawant

Address: Department of Pharmaceutics, Shree Sureshdada Jain Institute of Pharmaceutical Education & Research Jamner Dist Jalgaon 424206 Maharashtra, India

Email ✉: sawantabhay143@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Oral Drug Delivery :

Oral drug delivery method is the most widely utilized routes for administration among all alternatives that have been explored for systemic delivery of drug via various pharmaceutical products of different dosage forms.(1,2,3,4,5) With many drugs, the basic goal is to achieve a steady state blood level that is therapeutically effective and non-toxic for an extended period of time. The design of proper dosage form is an important element to accomplish this goal. Sustained release, sustained action, prolonged action, controlled release, extended action, timed release and depot dosage form as term used to identify drug delivery system that are designed to achieve prolonged therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of a single dose. In the case of oral sustained released dosage form, an effect is for several hours depending upon residence time of formulation in the GIT.(5,6) Conventional drug therapy requires periodic doses of therapeutic agents. These agents are formulated to produce maximum stability, activity and bioavailability. For most drugs, conventional methods of drug administration are effective, but some drugs are unstable or toxic and have narrow therapeutic ranges. Some drugs also possess solubility problems. In such cases, a method of continuous administration of therapeutic agent is desirable to maintain fixed plasma levels. To overcome these problems, controlled drug delivery systems were introduced three decades ago. These delivery systems have a number of advantages over traditional systems such as improved efficiency, reduced, toxicity, and improved patient convenience.(7,8)

Sustained release dosage forms : Any drug or dosage form modification that prolongs the

therapeutic activity of the drug. The release of the drug is retarded for a delayed and prolonged period of time in the systemic circulation. Sustained release formulation maintains a uniform blood level of drug with better patient compliance as well as increased efficacy of drug.(9,10,11) Sustained release tablets are generally taken once or twice a day during a course of treatment whereas in conventional dosage forms there is need to take 3-4 times dosage in a day to achieve the same therapeutic action. The regular measurement structures are quickly supplanted by this novel's sustained discharge procedures. The terms Sustained Release, Delayed Release or Prolong Release formulations are utilized to recognize drug delivery systems that are intended to accomplish or expand therapeutic impact by ceaselessly discharging medicine over an all-encompassing period of time after administration of a unit dose.(12,13) Any drug or measurement structure adjustment that draws out the therapeutic action of the drug. The arrival of the drug is hindered for a postponed and delayed period of time in the fundamental circulation.

MATERIALS AND METHOD :

Vildagliptin was purchased from Sun Pharma Industries LTD. Silvasa.

MCC,Lactose, HPMCK100M,Magnesium sterate,talc were purchased from Jinendra Scientific .

Preparation of SR Tablet of Vildagliptin :

1. All the ingredients were accurately weighed.
2. All weighed ingredients sifted separately with appropriate sieve/mesh (#60).
3. Pvp k30 [binder] mixed with purified water at quantity sufficient. And prepare binder solution
4. This solution add frequently in weighed drug and excipients and make a dum mass.
5. Make the small granules and Dry it.

6. This dried granules pass into sieve no. #22
7. Add it in lubricant and glidant passing from sieve no. #60
8. All the prepared powder fill in the container
9. Compressed with Using 9mm Punch in Hydraulic press.

Fig no 1 Hydraulic Press

Evaluation of SR Tablet :

1. Appearance:

The tablets were visually observed for capping, chipping and lamination.

2. Tablet dimensions/thickness:

The thickness of the tablets was determined by using vernier callipers. Randomly 10 tablets selected were used for determination of thickness that expressed in Mean $\pm$ SD and unit is mm.

Fig. No 2: Thickness determination by vernier caliper apparatus

3. Hardness

The hardness of a tablet determines its resistance to shipping, breakage, storage, transportation, and handling before use. The hardness of 20 tablets from each formulation was determined using the Monsanto Hardness Tester. The tablet was held in between the tester's two jaws along its oblong axis. At this point, the reading should be zero kg/cm². Then constant force was applied by rotating the tablet fractured.

4. Friability:

Friability is the loss of weight of tablet in the container due to removal of fine particles from the

surface during transportation or handling. Roche friabilator was employed for finding the friability of the tablets. For tablets with an average weight of 0.65 g or less take a sample of whole tablets corresponding to about 6.5 g and for tablets with an average weight of more than 0.65 g take a sample of 10 whole tablets. Roche friabilator was rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes for 100 rounds. A loss of less than 1% in weight in generally considered acceptable. Percent friability was calculated as follows,

$$\text{Percent Friability \% F} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

5. Weight variation test:

To determine weight variation, 20 tablets of each formulation were individually weighed using an electronic balance, the average weight was calculated, and the individual tablet weight was then compared to the average value.

Table No. 1: Specification for tablets as per USP

Average Weight Of Tablet	% Deviation
130 mg or less	10
More than 130 mg or less than 324 mg	7.5
324 or more	5

6. Drug content:

Ten tablets from each batch were precisely weighed and powdered. The powdered equivalent to 100 mg vildagliptin was weighed and shaken in 100ml of Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8 in a volumetric

flask, and 1ml was pipetted out and diluted up to 10 ml. The resulting solution was filtered and measured at 224 nm, and the vildagliptin content was calculated. It was calculated by using formula,

$$\text{Drug Content} = \frac{\text{Test absorbance}}{\text{Standard absorbance}} \times 100$$

7. Diameter:

Tablet diameter is dependent on the dimensions of the punch tip or punch face so it is critically checked or verified before installation of tooling on the compression machine/other. Example- Suppose we want to compress a batch of tablets in a round shape having a diameter of 8.0 mm. so for this purpose, we will use round-shaped punches & dies. To produce 8.0 mm round tablets the diameter of punches used should always be 8.0 mm.

do not give much importance to it, but it is most critical check because if our tablet diameter or dimensions are not according to specifications it will create problems not only during tablet blistering but will also lead to deviation and batch reprocessing.

Procedure For Measuring Tablet Diameter-

Like the tablet thickness test, the diameter of tablets is also measured using vernier calipers. If tablets are round simply, we measure the diameter by placing round tablets in the jaws of the vernier caliper one by one and take readings displayed on the digital vernier caliper.

Tooling Verification-

The tablet diameter testing is an unofficial test so most of the person in the pharmaceutical industry

Fig. No. 3: Determination of Diameter of Vildagliptin SRT by Vernier Caliper

8. In-vitro dissolution studies:

The USP dissolution test apparatus (apparatus II paddle type) was used to study the drug release from the tablets. The dissolution medium was 900ml of 0.1 N HCl. The release was performed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, with rotation speed 50 rpm. 5ml of sample was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals and replaced with fresh medium. The

samples were analyzed after appropriate dilution by UV spectrophotometer 1800 at 228 nm and drug release was determined by following formula,

RESULT AND DISCUSSION :

Preformulation Studies:

1.Organoleptic properties of Vildagliptin:

Table No.2: Organoleptic properties of vildagliptin

Sr. No.	Properties	Specification	Observation
1	Colour	A white crystalline powder	A crystalline powder
2	Odour	Odourless	Odourless
3	Taste	Bitter	Bitter

2 Melting point determination:

Table No. 3. Melting point of vildagliptin:

Drug (Vildagliptin)	Melting point apparatus	DSC (sharp peak)
Standard	148 °C - 152 °C	148 °C - 152 °C
Observed	151 °C	155 °C

3 Solubility:

Table No.4 : Solubility of Vildagliptin

Sr. No.	Media	Solubility (gm/ml)	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	1 M NaOH	0.0100	10
2	0.1 N HCL	0.009	9
3	0.01 N HCL	0.004	4
4	0.001 N HCL	0.002	2

Estimation of Vildagliptin:

Fig. No.4: Spectrum of vildagliptin

2 Standard calibration curve of vildagliptin in 0.1 N HCl

Table No. 5. Absorbance of Vildagliptin:

Sr. No.	Concentration (µ/ml)	Absorbance
1	1	5
2	2	10
3	3	15
4	4	20
5	5	25

Fig. No 5: Calibration curve of vildagliptin:

Standard Calibration Curve of Vildagliptin in 6.8 pH buffer:

Fig no 6 : Standard Calibration Curve of Vildagliptin in 6.8 pH buffer

Determination of solubility of vildagliptin in water:

Table No. 6. Absorbance of vildagliptin in water

Concentration (µ/ml)	Temperature (°C)	Absorbance	Solubility
5	25	0.255	0.1679
10	35	0.351	0.3358
15	45	0.479	0.5037
20	55	0.592	0.6717
25	65	0.649	0.8396

Fig. No.7 : Solubility curve of vildagliptin in water

**Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy:
Vildagliptin :**

Fig No. 8 : FTIR of vildagliptin

Table No 7: FTIR interpretation of vildagliptin

Characteristic functional group	Given Range (cm ⁻¹)	Observed peak (cm ⁻¹)
N-H stretching	3500-3100	3292.49
C-H stretching	3000-2850	2812.51
O-H stretching	3400-2400	2848.86
CN	2260-2240	—
C=O stretching	1680-1630	1653.00
CH ₂ bending	1465	1448.54

Fig no. 9 : FTIR spectrum of Vildagliptin + PVPK 30 + HPMC K 100M

Table No .8: FTIR Interpretation of Vildagliptin + PVPK 30 + HPMC K 100M

Characteristic Functional Group	Given Range (cm ⁻¹)	Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)
C-H	2800-3000	2907.958
C=C	1626-1662	1654-668
C-H	1360-1375	1363
C-O	1200-1285	1285

C-O	1075-1163	1163
C=C	665-795	792

Fig no. 10: FTIR spectrum of HPMCK 100 M + PVPK30
Table No. 9: FTIR Interpretation of HPMCK 100 M + PVP

Characteristic Functional Group	Given Range (cm ⁻¹)	Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)
C-H	2800-3000	2896
C=C	1626-1662	1647
C-H	1400-1450	1420
C-O	1200-1285	1284

Differential scanning calorimetry :

The DSC thermogram showed the sharp endothermic peak at 148.22 °C represented the melting point of vildagliptin.

Fig No.11: DSC Thermogram of pure vildagliptin

Fig No. 12: DSC thermogram of vildagliptin + all blend

Table No.11: Thermal transition & enthalpy values of vildagliptin & vildagliptin with all excipients

Sr. No.	Chemical	DSC Thermal Transition (°C)	Enthalpy (J/g)
1.	Vildagliptin	151 °C	-19.76 J/g

Evaluation of Tablet: Pre-compression parameters of preliminary trial batches of vildagliptin tablet :

Table No.12: Pre-compression parameters of preliminary trial batches of Sustained release tablets of vildagliptin

Batches	Angle of repose (θ)	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr`s index (%)	Hausner`s ratio
B1	28.5 ±0.022	0.643 ±0.021	0.785±0.010	14.22±1.551	1.22±0.051
B2	27.8 ±0.016	0.658 ±0.011	0.789±0.007	20.15±1.630	1.21±0.021
B3	26.3 ±0.022	0.633 ±0.028	0.792±0.008	14.83±2.719	1.26±0.047
B4	26.5 ±0.014	0.699 ±0.005	0.801±0.011	20.33±1.021	1.28±0.041
B5	27.3 ±0.001	0.687 ±0.001	0.788±0.037	18.217±2.35	1.27±0.049
B6	28.2 ±0.033	0.673 ±0.032	0.781±0.013	17.42±1.105	1.22±0.033
B7	28.2 ±0.03	0.678 ± 0.032	0.786 ± 0.012	16.98 ± 1.109	1.22 ± 0.33
B8	27.5 ± 0.025	0.654 ± 0.024	0.789 ± 0.024	17.87 ± 1.023	1.32 ± 0.32

All precompression parameters of preliminary trial batches shown satisfactory results as per their standard limits.

Table no. 13: Evaluation of Post-compression parameters of preliminary trial batches of Sustained release tablets of vildagliptin

Batches	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Weight variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
B1	4.87 ±0.01	3.07 ±0.05	197 ±0.86	0.76 ±0.012	80.31
B2	4.84 ±0.003	3.01 ±0.02	199 ±0.02	0.32 ±0.127	77.95
B3	4.88 ±0.001	3.09 ±0.07	199 ±0.01	0.82 ±0.061	85.82
B4	4.84±0 .004	3.07 ±0.05	197 ±0.08	0.72 ±0.122	102.36
B5	4.86 ±0.003	3.05 ±0.04	196 ±0.08	0.37 ±0.138	92.91
B6	4.83 ±0.002	3.04 ±0.02	198 ±0.08	0.78 ±0.325	88.97

B7	4.98 ± 0.03	3.04 ± 0.03	199 ± 0.06	0.67 ± 0.234	89.78
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Table No.14 : Post compression parameters of preliminary trial batches of Sustained release tablets of vildagliptin

Batches	Diameter (mm)	Water absorption ratio (%)	Wetting Time (Sec)
B1	8.09	70.55	30
B2	8.07	69.84	36
B3	8.05	70.85	40
B4	8.06	69.19	29
B5	8.06	74.48	37
B6	8.04	77.00	42
B7	8.08	74.76	45
B8	8.07	72.32	42

The post compression parameters of preliminary trial batches showed satisfactory results among all batches (B1-B9)

In-vitro drug release of preliminary trial batches of vildagliptin SRT tablet

Table No.15: % In-vitro drug release

Time (Hr)	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9
0	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	0
0.5	16.65	16.34	15.34	12.54	13.23	14.23	13.98	13.13	14.56
1	23.63	25.34	24.34	19.22	21.20	34.22	32.23	21.56	25.55
2	30.12	32.21	39.82	22.84	39.67	44.39	31.93	29.87	31.65
3	35.76	37.65	46.76	28.33	41.12	51.23	38.32	35.39	39.32
4	42.19	47.12	52.80	36.11	44.41	59.13	43.34	41.24	42.11
5	46.89	51.23	57.12	40.23	57.24	63.32	49.43	46.90	47.99
6	53.88	57.84	63.05	47.74	60.12	67.11	56.56	54.25	55.32
7	65.65	63.07	68.97	59.43	73.23	72.46	63.33	68.66	63.1
8	73.40	75.34	77.12	79.07	89.04	77.98	77.76	76.35	76.92
12	94.82	91.47	86.13	85.19	91.03	91.61	95.67	96.56	94.77

Fig No.13 : In-vitro Drug Release Profile of Preliminary Trial Batches of Sustained Release Tablet of Vildagliptin (B1-B9) Batches.

Evaluation of batches of IRT of vildagliptin generated by CCD:

Table No.15. Pre-compression Parameter of Batches Generated by CCD

Batches	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Compressibility index (%)	Hausner`s ratio	Angle of Repose (θ)
B1	0.42 ±0.03	0.48 ±0.04	12.50 ±0.05	1.14 ±0.03	26.09 ±0.02
B2	0.39 ±0.07	0.45 ±0.05	13.33 ±0.04	1.15 ±0.02	27.16 ±0.04
B3	0.35 ±0.02	0.41 ±0.03	14.63 ± 0.02	1.17 ±0.04	25.57 ±0.06
B4	0.39 ±0.04	0.50 ±0.04	18.12 ±0.06	1.13 ±0.02	26.38 ±0.05
B5	0.41 ±0.05	0.47 ±0.06	11.11 ±0.03	1.12 ±0.05	28.94 ±0.03
B6	0.36 ±0.03	0.45 ±0.04	20.04 ±0.07	1.13 ±0.07	28.43 ±0.03
B7	0.38 ±0.02	0.43 ±0.02	10.64 ±0.01	1.13 ±0.03	29.10 ±0.02
B8	0.40 ±0.04	0.45 ±0.05	18.69 ±0.02	1.14 ±0.02	27.64 ±0.04
B9	0.46 ±0.05	0.52 ±0.03	11.54 ±0.03	1.17 ±0.04	25.18 ±0.05

Table No.16: Post-compression Parameter of Batches Generated by CCD

Batches	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Weight variation (mg)	Wetting time (sec)
B1	4.55 ± 0.01	4.13 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.86	36
B2	4.62 ± 0.01	4.11 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.5	30
B3	4.52 ± 0.01	4.31 ± 0.01	198 ± 0.70	25
B4	4.6 ± 0.01	4.3 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.70	30
B5	4.55 ± 0.01	4.19 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.70	30
B6	4.55 ± 1	4.12 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.39	40
B7	4.45 ± 0.01	4.13 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.70	42
B8	4.79 ± 0.01	4.3 ± 0.01	197 ± 0.70	33
B9	5.13 ± 0.01	4.21 ± 0.01	198 ± 0.70	32

Table No.17: Post-compression Parameter of Batches Generated by CCD

Batches	Friability (%)	Diameter (mm)	Water absorption ratio (%)	Drug Content (%)
B1	0.41 ± 0.01	8.09	69.19	93.70%
B2	0.60 ± 0.01	8.05	70.35	96.06%
B3	0.7 ± 0.01	8.09	73.36	98.42%
B4	0.62 ± 0.01	8.08	70.70	100.78%
B5	0.46 ± 0.01	8.06	73.97	92.91%
B6	0.50 ± 0.01	8.14	85.07	98.20%
B7	0.63 ± 0.01	8.12	81.09	90.55%
B8	0.66 ± 0.01	8.07	78.78	88.97%
B9	0.7 ± 0.01	8.09	72.08	97.63%

Table No.18: % In-vitro drug release of batches by DOE software:

Time (min)	% Drug Release Batches								
	VLD1	VLD2	VLD3	VLD4	VLD5	VLD6	VLD7	VLD8	VLD9
0	0	0	0	0	00	0	0	0	0
0.5	14.67	13.23	17.88	13.66	13.23	13.43	13.33	15.32	14.56
1	23.56	19.78	25.66	31.55	21.20	24.56	35.12	17.88	35.12
2	31.17	25.50	31.17	42.51	39.67	34.00	39.67	22.67	41.09
3	38.40	36.45	44.77	46.11	41.12	38.66	42.98	30.43	44.30
4	44.63	44.63	58.80	50.30	44.41	40.38	45.34	37.55	50.30
5	49.52	50.66	61.98	54.99	57.24	45.66	55.66	43.60	56.67
6	53.84	61.64	63.05	59.51	60.12	50.30	60.22	47.46	58.09
7	72.26	82.89	77.22	78.64	73..23	77.22	76.51	74.39	79.35
8	84.31	97.77	87.06	82.18	89.04	80.85	77.22	77.22	80.76
12	86.65	88	90	87	91.03	89.90	100.01	99.98	102.12

Fig No.14: In-Vitro Drug Released Study of Optimized Batches of Vildagliptin SRT Generated by CCD (B1-B9).

Table No.19: Comparison of Percentage Drug Released of Optimized Formulation (B5) of Vildagliptin SRT of Vildagliptin and Marketed Uncoated Tablet

Sr. No.	Time (min)	%DR of B5	Time (min)	%DR of Marketed Product
1	00	00	00	00
2	05	42.51	05	22.22
3	10	51.32	10	35.84
4	15	60.63	15	47.91
5	30	78.11	30	75.12
6	45	82.11	45	80.84
7	60	96.62	60	86.12

Fig No. 15: Comparison of In-Vitro Drug Released of Optimized Batch B5 and Marketed Formulation (Vylida 50 mg) Uncoated 2 Tablets of Vildagliptin

Optimization and Data Analysis: Optimization:

Table No.20: Result of optimization batches by Central Composite Design:

Batches	X1	X2	% Drug Release (%)
B1	+1	-1	85
B2	+α	0	88
B3	+1	+1	93
B4	0	+α	95
B5	-α	0	96
B6	0	0	98.5
B7	0	-α	100.01
B8	-1	-1	99.98
B9	-1	+1	102.12

Data Analysis:

A. %Drug Release:

Table No.21: Result of Analysis of Variance for Batches by CCD of Vildagliptin Sustained Release Tablet

	DF*	SS*	MS*	F*	P Value	
Model	2	0.5874	0.1958	7.83	0.0246	Significant
Residual	6	0.1250	0.0250	—	—	
Total	8	0.7124	—	—	—	

* DF indicates degree of freedom; SS sum of square; MS mean sum of square and F is Fischer's ration.

Fig No.16 : Response Surface Contour Graph Showing the Influence of HPMC k100m (A1) and PVPK30 (B1) on % Drug Release (Y1)

Fig No.17 : 3D Response Surface Graph Showing the Influence of HPMCK100M A1) and PVPK30 (B1) on % Drug Release (Y1)

Stability Study:

I) Accelerated Stability Study

Table No.22: Accelerated Stability Data for B5 Optimized Batch of Vildagliptin SRT

Parameters		Condition 40±2°C/75%±5 RH		
		Initial	1 Month	2 Month
Physical	Average Weight (mg)	200	199	198
	Thickness (mm)	4.0	4.0	4.1
	Hardness (Kg/Cm ²)	4.10	4.20	4.20
	Friability (%)	0.52	0.52	0.50
	DT. Sec.		38	38
		36		
Chemical	% Drug Release (%)	96.00	96.00	96.00
	Drug Content (%)	98.20	99.78	101.13

II) Long term Stability Study

Table No. 23 : Accelerated Stability Data for B5 Optimized Batch of Vildagliptin SRT

Parameters		Condition 30±20C/65%±5 RH		
		Initial	1 Month	2 Month
Physical	Average Weight (mg)	200	198	197
	Thickness (mm)	4.0	4.0	4.1
	Hardness (Kg/Cm ²)	4.10	4.10	4.20
	Friability (%)	0.52	0.54	0.55
Chemical	% Drug Release	99.39	99.10	98.67

	Drug Content (%)	98.20	99.78	101.35
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III) Long Term Stability Study (Store in Refrigerator)

Table No 24: Long Term (Stored in Refrigerator) Stability Data for B5 Optimized Batch of Vildagliptin SRT:

Parameters		Condition 2±80C		
		Initial	1 Month	2 Month
Physical	Average Weight (Mg)	200	199	197
	Thickness (mm)	4.0	3.9	3.9
	Hardness (Kg/Cm ²)	4.10	3.90	3.90
	Friability (%)	0.50	0.52	0.52
Chemical	% Drug Release (%)	99.39	99.02	98.84
	Drug Content (%)	98.20	98.17	98.16

Fig No.18: Stability studies of SRT of Vildagliptin in Environmental Test Chamber

CONCLUSION:

In present study an attempt has been made to prepare sustained release tablet. Vildagliptin was used as model drug. Suitable analytical method based on UV Visible spectrophotometer was developed for estimation of Vildagliptin. The polymer selected for the sustaining the release i.e HPMC K100M, PVPK30 is compatible with Vildagliptin confirmed by FT-IR analysis. Wet granulation technique was established for preparation of sustained release tablet of

vildagliptin. Preliminary trial batches of sustained release tablets of vildagliptin were successfully prepared using HPMC K100M, PVPK30. From the results of preliminary batches helps to find out optimum concentration of release retarding polymer. The CCD designs were selected & can be successfully applied for formulation of factorial batches using combination of polymer. The pre & post compression parameter were evaluated and was found within acceptable limit. The selected independent variable exhibit the significant effect

on dependent variables. The polymer used showed better control over the percentage drug release. Chosen experimental design was found to be very useful tool in the development of Vildagliptin and allow minimum possible number of experimental run and rapid systematic and reliable screening to identify and quantitatively define the significant formulation factor influencing the drug release.

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